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Research Article

EFFICIENCY OF ESWL WITH OR WITHOUT DOUBLE J- URETERIC STENT

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Abstract:

Objective: To evaluate role of extracorporeal shock waves lithotripsy (ESWL) in patients having 15-35mm renal stones with and without double-j-ureteric stent.

Design & duration: This is a comparative interventional study completed in 12 months duration

Setting:

Patients & methods: Patients admitted to urology ward of study hospital carrying renal stones of 15-35mm were included in the study. These cases were divided into two groups, in one group patients were treated with ESWL without double-j ureteric stent and in other group ESWL was done with prior insertion of double-j ureteric stent. Detailed history was taken from all cases about signs and symptoms of renal stones. Thorough examination was done as well. Baseline and specific laboratory investigations were done, renal stone was diagnosed on plain X-ray and ultrasonography of KUB and intravenous urography. Patients of either sex or age between 15-55 years having renal stone of 10-30mm were included in the study. A performa was designed in which important findings on history, examination and investigations were documented. Patients having co-morbid conditions, unfit for general anesthesia were excluded from the study.

Results: Total 90 cases were studied including 57.8% male and 42.2% female cases. Mean age of cases was 34.2±8.6 years. In 18.9% cases stone size was 10-20mm and in 81.1% cases stone size was 20-30mm. In 50% cases D.J stent was inserted, while in other 50% D.J stent was inserted prior to ESWL. After ESWL, main complications were pain in 31% cases and urinary retention in 26.7% cases. Stones location was upper calyx in 17.8% cases, middle calyx in 25.5% cases, lower calyx in 12.2% cases and pelvis in 44.4% cases.

Conclusion: It is concluded that ESWL with double-J ureteric stent is much effective and safe having less complications as compared to ESWL without double-J ureteric stent.

Key words: Extracorporeal shock waves Lithotripsy, Renal stones, Double-J ureteric stent

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INTRODUCTION:

Urolithiasis is a high prevalent disease worldwide affecting 10-15% population of world. Recent development in medical field has emphasized on minimal invasive procedures for the treatment of urolithiasis. There are various modes of treatment such as conservative treatment with medicines, open surgical removal of stone, percutaneous nephrolithotomy and ESWL. Mode of treatment depends on stone size, number of stones, composition, location of stone in urinary tract, co-morbidities, renal anomalies, age of patient and failure of other modes of treatment.¹ Urolithiasis is a disease of ancient times. It is a painful condition and life threatening if untreated. Many old ways of treatment have proved unsuccessful and sometimes dangerous as well.² In early eighties, surgery and endoscopic technique were introduced for the treatment of urolithiasis. In 1980 extracorporeal shock waves lithotripsy (ESWL) was introduced as a minimally invasive technique to treat urinary stones when one patient was successfully treated by this procedure.³ Although it is an expensive mode of treatment, it has become much common in whole world and now commonly used in well-equipped healthcare set-ups. ESWL is an out-patient procedure.⁴ For this treatment patient does not need to be admitted in Hospital and morbidity and mortality associated with surgery and anesthesia can be avoided. In recurrent renal stones surgery causes high rate of morbidity and mortality, so in such cases minimal invasive procedure like ESWL is treatment of choice and easily acceptable by the patient.⁵ Incidence of renal stones is increasing worldwide with the passage of time. It has high recurrence rate. It has metabolic, biochemical, genetic and environmental risk factors. Upper urinary tract stones are usually seen in developed countries due to more use of proteins and calcium and their incidence is increasing in tropical Africa, while lower urinary tract stones are common in developing

and under developed countries. In Ghana incidence of upper urinary tract stones is 2/100,000.⁶

PATIENTS & METHODS:

This is a comparative interventional study conducted in urology department of Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Medical University Larkana. Study was started in June 2019 and completed after 12 months in May 2020. Patients admitted to urology ward of study hospital carrying renal stones of 15-35mm were included in the study. These cases were divided into two groups, in one group patients were treated with ESWL without double-j ureteric stent and in other group ESWL was done with prior insertion of double-j ureteric stent. Detailed history was taken from all cases about signs and symptoms of renal stones. Thorough examination was done as well. Baseline and specific laboratory investigations were done, renal stone was diagnosed on plain X-ray and ultrasonography of KUB and intravenous urography. Patients of either sex or age between 15-55 years having renal stone of 10-30mm were included in the study. A proforma was designed in which important findings on history, examination and investigations were documented. Patients having co-morbid conditions, unfit for general anesthesia were excluded from the study. After treatment follow up visits were planned at intervals of 7-30 days. After stone removal it was sent for biochemical examination to determine its composition. Treatment was considered successful if residual stone of 4mm or smaller size is left behind.

RESULTS:

Total 90 cases were studied including 52(57.8%) male and 38(42.2%) female cases. Mean age of cases was 34.2±8.6 years. There were 7(7.8%) cases having age 15-25 years, 28(31.1%) cases between 26-35 years, 35(38.8%) cases were between 36-45 years and 20(21.7%) cases were having age >45 years.

(Table-1) Age distribution of patients in study group (n=90)

Age of patients (years)	N	%
15-25	7	7.8
26-35	28	31.1
36-45	35	38.8
>45	20	21.7

In 17(18.9%) cases stone size was 10-20mm and in 81.1% cases stone size was 20-30mm. In 50% cases D.J stent was inserted, while in other 50% D.J stent was inserted prior to ESWL. After ESWL, main complications were pain in 31% cases and urinary retention in 26.7% cases. Stones location was upper calyx in 17.8% cases, middle calyx in 25.5% cases, lower calyx in 12.2% cases and pelvis in 44.4% cases.

(Figure-1) Frequency of different locations of stone in urinary tract in study group

(Table-2) Frequency of ESWL sessions done in study group

Stone size	No. of cases	No. of ESWL sessions				
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th
<20 mm	17	12 (70.5%)	3(17.6%)	2(11.8%)		
>20mm	73	16(21.9%)	33(45.2%)	28(38.4%)	8(10.9%)	5(6.8%)

(Table-3) Duration of stone clearance after ESWL according to size of stone

Duration of stone clearance (days)	Patients without double-J ureteric stent (n=45)		Patients with double-J ureteric stent (n=45)	
	N	%Age	N	%
Stone size <20mm (n=17)				
10-20	1	10%	0	0
21-30	3	30%	2	28.5%
31-40	2	20%	4	57.1%
41-50	4	40%	1	14.3%
Total	10	100%	7	100
Stone Size >20mm (n=73)				
20-30	3	8.6%	2	5.3%
31-40	3	8.6%	8	21.1%
41-50	4	11.4%	21	55.3%
51-60	8	22.8%	5	3.2%
>60	17	48.6%	2	5.3%
Total	35	100%	38	100%

(Table-4) Frequency of complications reported in study group after ESWL

Complications	Patients without double-J ureteric stent (n=45)		Patients with double-J ureteric stent (n=45)	
	N	%Age	N	%Age
Pain	15	33.3%	13	28.9%
Steinstrasse	11	24.4%	2	4.4%
UTI	5	11.1%	12	26.7%
Haematuria	16	35.5%	15	33.3%
Urinary retention	22	48.9%	2	4.4%
Perirenal hematoma	7	15.5%	2	4.4%

(Figure-2) Gender wise distribution of cases in study group (n=90)**DISCUSSION:**

Incidence of urinary tract stones is variable depending on geographical areas. Industrialized countries have higher prevalence than developing and third world countries. ESWL was first time used by Chaussy in 1980.⁷ Being a minimal invasive procedure it has low morbidity and preferred by patients. In 80% cases of renal stones ESWL is a primary mode of treatment. Initially this procedure was used for small stones in renal pelvis but now its indications have been increased.⁸ This technique has reduced indications for open surgery in renal stones removal. It is more suitable for stones in upper urinary tract. A study done by Jan Muhammad 70% were male and 30% were female cases.⁹ It is similar to our study where majority of cases 57.8% are male. In our study, patients were having variation of age with age range of 15-55 years and mean age of 34.2±8.6 years. While study of Kangjam Sholay reported mean age of patients 43.8 years.¹⁰ Large stones need more sessions of ESWL, despite of this it is widely used as patient does not need anesthesia, hospital admission and it is minimal invasive.¹¹ Small size stones need less number of sessions with

much better outcomes. In our study ESWL was used in large size stones and results were much satisfying with good outcomes. It can also be used in combination therapy with PCNL.¹² A study conducted in Iraq reported success rate of 50-90% after ESWL in patients with renal stones.¹³ Urolithiasis is a high prevalent disease worldwide affecting 10-15% population of world. Recent development in medical field has emphasized on minimal invasive procedures for the treatment of urolithiasis. There are various modes of treatment such as conservative treatment with medicines, open surgical removal of stone, percutaneous nephrolithotomy and ESWL. Mode of treatment depends on stone size, number of stones, composition, location of stone in urinary tract, comorbidities, renal anomalies, age of patient and failure of other modes of treatment. In our study 17.8% stones were in upper calyx, 25.5% stones were in middle calyx, 12.2% were in lower calyx and 44.4% stones were in pelvis. It showed mostly stones were on pelvis of kidney. These results are comparable to a similar study in which 20.7% cases had stones in pelvicalyx, 71% cases had stones in

renal pelvis, 1.9% had stones in upper calyx, 0.9% had stones in middle calyx and 4.8% cases had stones in lower calyx.¹⁴ According to in vitro studies, in ESWL low frequency and high voltage is associated with improved fragmentation of stone.¹⁵ Many hospital in our country are treating urinary tract stones successfully with monotherapy of ESWL with high success rate. Previously data is deficient on ESWL use in stone removal of >20mm size.¹⁶

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that ESWL with double-J ureteric stent is much effective and safe having less complications as compared to ESWL without double-J ureteric stent. Outcomes of double-J ureteric stent were better than without double-J ureteric stent with early removal of calculi and smaller residual stone.

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